

Konstantin Berest

**EFFICIENT PRODUCT PRICING MODEL
AS A FACTOR IN INCREASING AN IT COMPANY
COMPETITIVENESS**

This article analyses the most popular product pricing strategies as a factor in increasing an IT company's competitiveness. We are analyzing the best practices used by most IT companies.

There are two main pricing approaches in the market: cost-based and value-based. The cost-based approach includes three models: Dedicated Team, Time and material, and a Fixed Price.

A Dedicated Team is a model in which a company provides a team of specific professionals for a specific time. Such a scheme minimizes product-related risks for a team provider but also does not give control over the final product. Such a scheme would increase the competitiveness of companies with decent expertise in a particular domain but with limited resources for their own production. In a Time and Material model, one divides a project into several tasks, estimating them approximately. Such an approach allows for a more objective assessment of the cost. This model would increase a company's competitiveness by minimizing the uncertainty risks of both parties – the IT company and their client (regardless if it is a B2C or a B2B solution). A Fixed price model stands for paying a fixed amount for a certain amount of work. It is advantageous due to an accurately predicted result and minimal risk for the customer. This model can increase a company's competitiveness by making its service or product more attractive to customers (in both B2C and B2B sectors).

A value-based approach is more innovative. This approach is based on the customer's perception of the service, not on the cost of the service. Such a pricing approach allows companies to build long-term relations with customers, increasing their loyalty and even allowing the company to set a price that has nothing to do with the actual spent on a product or a service.

To sum up, an effective product pricing strategy may increase the IT company's competitiveness.

Key words: IT company, IT service, IT product, pricing model, competitiveness.

Берест К. В. Вибір ефективної моделі ціноутворення продукту в ІТ-компанії як чинник підвищення конкурентоздатності.

У статті подано аналіз найбільш популярних стратегій ціноутворення продукту як фактору підвищення конкурентоздатності ІТ-компанії. Розглянуто найбільш ефективні практики, якими користується більшість ІТ-компаній.

На ринку існує два основних підходи до ціноутворення: підхід, заснований на витратах, і підхід, заснований на цінності. Підхід, заснований на витратах, містить три моделі: «виділена команда», «час і матеріали» та «фіксована ціна». Виділена команда – це модель, за якою компанія надає команду певних професіоналів на визначений час. Така схема мінімізує для постачальника команди пов'язані з продуктом ризики, але також не дає контролю над кінцевим продуктом. Така схема може сприяти конкурентоздатності компаній з великим досвідом у певній галузі, але з обмеженими ресурсами для власного виробництва. У моделі «час і матеріал» проект розбивають на кілька окремих завдань, кожному з яких дають приблизну оцінку. Такий підхід дозволяє краще оцінити вартість. Ця модель може підвищити конкурентоздатність компанії за рахунок мінімізації ризиків невизначеності обох сторін – ІТ-компанії та її клієнта (незалежно від того, хто є клієнтом – інший бізнес чи кінцевий споживач). Модель фіксованої ціни передбачає оплату фіксованої суми за певний обсяг роботи. Це вигідно завдяки точно прогнозованому результату та мінімальному ризику для клієнта. Така модель може підвищити конкурентоздатність компанії, зробивши її послугу або продукт більш привабливими для клієнтів (для іншого бізнесу чи кінцевого споживача).

Ціннісно-орієнтований підхід є більш інноваційним. Цей підхід базується на сприйнятті послуги чи продукту клієнтом, а не на реальній вартості послуги чи продукту. Такий підхід до ціноутворення дозволяє компаніям будувати довгострокові відносини з клієнтами, підвищуючи їх лояльність і навіть дозволяючи компанії встановлювати ціну, яка має мало спільного з фактичними витратами на продукт або послугу.

Таким чином, ефективна модель ціноутворення продукту може бути фактором підвищення конкурентоздатності ІТ-компанії.

Ключові слова: ІТ-компанія, ІТ-послуги, ІТ-продукт, модель ціноутворення, конкурентоздатність.

The IT market has shown massive growth within the past few decades. Its full potential seems far away from its current state, and we see new market players coming in and out, along with the billions of investments

being multiplied or spent in vain within months (not even years!). These facts make investors from the government and private sectors think of the main factors that allow one market participant to last longer and stay competitive and others – to leave the market soon after the launch.

The competitiveness of an IT company is a complex phenomenon that includes but is not limited to the company's product uniqueness, go-to-market strategy, product and company agility, scalability, and even global social trends.

The first thing that comes to mind when considering company success is revenue. We should also analyze the product the company offers ('product' stands here for both service and physical construction), the way it works with the people, and the time it comes to a market. However, we suggest putting these off so far because it would shift emphasis to the product. Let us start from the fundamental question – company pricing policy, which affects its competitiveness and cooperation with a potential consumer (regardless if it is a B2C or B2B solution).

Nowadays, there is no universal approach to the pricing model in IT. However, there are a few best practices used by the major big players and adopted by companies of different scales worldwide. We can distinguish two main pricing approaches in the market: a cost-based approach and an approach based on value.

The first one is easier and more common, so let us describe it first. It includes the following pricing models:

- Dedicated Team;
- Time and material;
- Fixed Price [1].

Let us have a closer look at these three. A Dedicated Team is a model in which a company and a client mutually agree on the project requirements and the workload for a specified time. For instance, for an outsourcing company, it would mean that they are to provide professionals that meet customers' requirements and are fully focused on the task. The client has complete managerial control over the project and the team, while the service provider is effectively the recruiter and provides administrative support [2].

We have started from this pricing option because, in such cases, the service provider role is reduced to a minimum after the team's formation.

Usually, cooperation under this model consists of several main stages: determination of team skills and size, search or training of those specialists by the service providing company, and finally, the team gathering and start of the work.

Such a scheme is widely used for complex projects where product development teams need to gain more professionals quickly but do not have resources for their hiring or training. For a 'team consumer' this scheme reduces people management costs but raises risks of not having complete control over the newbies joining their product [3]. For a team provider, this scheme is advantageous due to minimal product adoption-related risks, but it also gives no control over the final product.

Such a scheme would increase the competitiveness of companies with decent expertise in a particular domain but are limited in resources for their own production. We can even compare this strategy with a consulting service. However, a dedicated team does not only offer their knowledge but also participates in product development directly.

One of the most popular pricing models is The Time and material (T&M). This pricing model fits complex and complicated projects and product development, where it is hard to tell how long or hard the development process will be. It is also popular among products with an open goal (or simply without a clear vision of the final result), especially when it is impossible to divide the process into several smaller stages [4, 5].

This pricing approach is more effective than the fixed price because of the innovative nature of most IT products. It is easy to predict how long a well-known process will take, but the estimate is close to guessing when it comes to anything nobody has done before. E.g., one can tell that a team of four can paint a car in a week, but it is impossible to tell how long it will take to build a controller for a newly invented artificial blood pump.

For this reason, companies usually divide each project into several separate tasks, explaining their importance, complexity, execution method, and approximate cost (along with the confidence level for that estimate). Then the client can determine the order and method of performing tasks given their price and importance for the project. Such an approach allows for a more objective assessment of the cost of the provided services.

Therefore, the time and materials pricing model works for projects that

are difficult to estimate (for example, for innovative projects) and require significant flexibility in the implementation process. This model would increase a company's competitiveness by minimizing the uncertainty risks of both parties – the IT company and their client (regardless if it is a B2C or a B2B solution).

The last (and the most common in the conditions of “traditional” industries) pricing model is the Fixed price. It is clear from the name that this option involves paying a fixed amount for a certain amount of work. The fixed price model is ideal for small to medium-sized projects where all requirements, specifications, and timelines can be clearly defined before the development starts. After the customer's request, the service-providing company analyzes the scope and complexity of the project and provides the project implementation schedule and a fixed budget for the customer's approval.

The main stages of work under this model are also quite “classical”: the customer submits a request with requirements, the executor and the customer discuss the details, the executor sends a proposal, a payment schedule, and a delivery schedule, which is then agreed upon by both parties and drawn up in the form of a contract. After fulfilling the terms of the contract (provision of services), the client accepts and approves the product [5].

The advantages of such a model are an accurately predicted result, minimal risk for the customer, and no need for constant control. However, this is the cause of specific difficulties – the exact planning process itself may require significant financial resources and time, and making changes during implementation is difficult and costly. In fact, the longer the development lasts, the more expensive a change or a mistake in initial requirements becomes. This model can increase a company's competitiveness by making its service or product more attractive to customers (in both B2C and B2B sectors).

It is worth remembering that the IT industry is one of the most innovative and dynamic, and the issue of pricing is also not static. In the global practice of production, the value-based model (by which we mean how valuable a product or service is to the consumer; consumer value) became a novelty at the end of the last century (approximately at the same time when people

came to understand the importance of product delivery or services). In production, it is challenging to use such an approach because usually, such a technique will lead to a significant price increase (due to the brand, prestige of the product, etc.). Moreover, production costs have a natural physical expression, so they usually cannot be overestimated. On the other hand, the sphere of services offers excellent opportunities for using this pricing strategy [3].

A value strategy focuses on a long-term relationship between the consumer and the service provider. It is based on the customer's perception of the service, not on the cost of the service.

From a marketing perspective, a pricing strategy's goal is to set a price that is the monetary equivalent of the value the customer sees in the product while maintaining a profit margin and return on investment. It is hard to disagree with this approach and with the fact that the traditional approach to assessing the value of IT services tends to be short-term and tactical and puts the interests of the provider above the interest of the customer. Conversely, the value approach is customer-based, strategic, and long-term, as it focuses on commercializing the value perception of each customer.

Companies that understand the strategic role of pricing and use a systematic approach to pricing, with an understanding of how customers value alternative services and the prices they are willing to pay, can make better decisions throughout the service development and implementation process. Buyers choose the most acceptable options based on how much the indicated price corresponds to the benefits that the customer will receive (of course, such an assessment is more than subjective) [6]. Such a pricing strategy increases the company's competitiveness by making its customers more loyal and building long-term relationships with individual customers, which leads to a brand awareness.

What affects the value of a product to a consumer? Value is the total benefit the customers receive at the price that they, as customers, are willing to pay. IT companies should first understand how their customers perceive value. Service providers must understand how to reach this trade-off and influence product and service configurations to maximize customer value and, as a result, business results. In our further explorations, we will

focus more on how customer value forms, what affects it, and how the company pricing model should interact with the overall company marketing plan.

Thus, after considering the most popular pricing models, we can state that each can be a factor in increasing the company's competitiveness. By choosing the most effective product pricing model for an IT company, a business entity can minimize its risks, compensate for the team's lack of experience, or, on the contrary, profitably sell its own experience and use the company's knowledge and material resources as efficiently as possible. The choice of pricing strategy will depend on the company's level of expertise in the niche, the volume of the material base for production, and the level of uncertainty in the requirements for the final product.

Список бібліографічних посилань

1. Голидзьбіна, А. В., Язвінська, Н. В. (2017) Особливості сучасного ринку IT-послуг та специфіка просування на ньому. *Економічний вісник Національного технічного університету України «Київський політехнічний інститут»*, 14, с. 23–36.
2. Яценко, М. С., Бут, Н. В. (2011) Управління витратами та тарифами з надання інфокомунікаційних послуг за допомогою сучасних інформаційних технологій. *Праці Одеського політехнічного університету*, 3, с. 177–183.
3. IT (мировой рынок). *Информационный портал TAdviser*. URL: <http://tadviser.ru/a/53627> 2018. (дата звернення: 14.12.2021).
4. Васильев, К. А. (2013). Влияние развития рынка информационных продуктов и услуг на конкурентоспособность субъектов хозяйствования. *Управленец*, 5, с. 9–10.
5. Иванова, О. А. (2017). Конкурентоспособность производственных и территориальных экономических систем. *Вчені зап. Харків. гуманітар. ун-ту «Нар. укр. акад.»*, т. 23, с. 182–188.
6. Пілюшенко В. Л. (2005). *Інформаційні технології у маркетингу і рекламі*. Донецьк, 204 с.

References

1. Holydybina, A. V., Yazvinska, N. V. (2017) Osoblyvosti suchasnoho rynku IT-poslulh ta spetsyfika prosuvannia na niomu [IT services market features and specifics of promotion on IT]. *Ekonomichniy visnyk Natsionalnoho tekhnichnoho universytetu Ukrainy «Kyivskiy politekhnichnyi instytut» [Economic Bulletin*

of National Technical University of Ukraine «Kyiv Polytechnic Institute»], 14, p. 23–36.

2. Yatsenko, M. S., But, N. V. (2011) Upravlinnia vytratamy ta taryfamy z nadannia infokommunikatsiinykh posluh za dopomohoiu suchasnykh informatsiinykh tekhnolohii [Managing costs and tariffs to provide infocommunication services through modern information technologies]. *Pratsi Odeskoho politekhnichnoho universytetu [Proceedings of Odessa Polytechnic University]*, 3, p. 177–183.

3. IT (mirovoyi rynok). Informatsyunny portal TAdviser [IT (world market). Information portal]. URL: <http://tadviser.ru/a/53627> 2018. (last viewed on 14.12.2021).

4. Vasylev, K. A. (2013). Vliyanie razvitiya rynku informatsyonykh produktov i uslug na konkurentosposobnost' subjektov khoziaystvovaniya [The effect of the development of IT products and services market on the competitiveness of a business entity]. *Upravlenets [Manager]*, 5, p. 9–10.

5. Ivanova, O. A. (2017). Competitiveness of production and territorial economic systems. *Vcheni zap. Kharkiv. humanitar. un-tu «Nar. ukr. akad.»* [Research bulletin of Kharkiv University of Humanities «People's Ukrainian akad.»], vol. 23, p. 182–188.

6. Piliushenko V. L. (2005). *Informatsiini tekhnolohii u marketynhu i reklami [Information technologies in marketing and advertisements]*. Donetsk, 204 p.